

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 1 |
January 2022 | Monthly Journal
by TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly Journal by **The World
Association of Scientists & Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Study on the Quality Standard of Rhubarb Qushang Pabu

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Accepted
Published

January 20,2022
January 22,2022

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Funding:

1) Pudong New Area Health System Discipline Leader Training Plan (PWRD2022-13). 2) Pudong New Area TCM Science and Technology Innovation Project (PDZY-2019-0805).

Copyright: © The Author(s); Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

How to cite this article: Nongzhang Xu, Min Chen, Cuihong Wang, Hongyang Tan, Qiyuan Wu (2022). Study on the Quality Standard of Rhubarb Qushang Pabu. *North American Academic Research*, 5(1), 16-24, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7490275>

ABSTRACT

Establish the quality control standard of rhubarb anti-trauma cataplasm. The qualitative analysis of rhubarb, angelica, and affective components of aloë-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin has been done with thin-layer chromatography (TLC) and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), respectively. The TLC spots of rhubarb and angelica in rhubarb antisurgery papu were clear, and the negative control had no interference. HPLC results demonstrate that high intense hydrophilic compound peaks are observed on the lower side; however, low intense peaks are towards the higher side of the scale. The intensity of these peaks is decreased from mixed reference solution to test solution and negative reference solution.

Keywords

Rhubarb Qushang Pabu, Thin-layer Chromatography, High Performance Liquid Chromatography, Assay, Quality Standard

Introduction

The herbs rhubarb is an everlasting medicine that belongs to the family of Polygonaceae. The word rhubarb was invented from the Latin term “rha,” called a river. However, the word “barb” means barbarian land. Because of its unlimited profits, this vegetable is generally signified as an amazing drug; along with this, it is also known as the wondrous drug. The medicine rhubarb is abundantly endowed with compounds like anthraquinone glycosides, tannins, stilbene glycosides (resveratrol and piceatannol), polysaccharides, volatile

oils, flavonoids, and saponins. Among all these compounds, tannins are the foremost dynamic compound of this class [The Wealth of India, 1999](#); [S.K. Bhattacharjee et al 2005](#).

Rhubarb herbs have wide use in various diseases like scalds, bleeding symptoms, red eyes, intestinal obstruction, throat soreness, abdominal abscess, dysentery, jaundice, traumatic injuries, carbuncles, and furuncles, missed periods, burns, and constipation. This herbal has a shortened purgative effect and is commonly used to treat carbuncles red eyes, gum swelling, and sore throat [W.C. Evan et al 2007](#); [S. Alam et al 2015](#). Rhubarb Qushang Ointment is an empirical formula widely used in Zhoupu Hospital for a long time. It has the effects of promoting blood circulation, relieving blood stasis, relieving pain, reducing swelling, cooling blood, and promoting blood circulation. It is mainly used for ankle sprains [X. Nongzhang et al 2016](#). The effect, due to its shortcomings, such as low drug loading, unstable drug release, short duration of drug effect, airtightness, and easy soiling of clothing, etc., its clinical application is limited to a certain extent. Rhubarb anti-injury cataplasm is a new dosage form developed by ointment. It consists of rhubarb, raw gardenia, Gansong, Angelica dahurica, angelica, safflower, camellia, Wangbuliuxing, trichosanthes, red peony, turmeric, frankincense, myrrh. It is of great significance for the composition of 14 traditional Chinese medicines such as camphor to establish a complete quality control standard to fully and effectively reflect the properties and ingredient content of the preparation [Bo Cao et al 2019](#).

Therefore, the qualitative analysis of rhubarb and angelica was carried out regarding relevant literature. At the same time, the content of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether was determined by the HPLC method [Azim Md Sabir et al 2015](#), and a complete quality control method was established to control the intrinsic properties of rhubarb anti-trauma cataplasm quality.

Materials and methods

Experimental materials

Rhubarb (Rhubarb palm) (batch number 121249-200402) was provided by the China National Institute for the Control of Pharmaceutical and Biological Products. Angelica (batch number 120927-200512), Rhein (batch number 110757-200005), and Ferulic acid (batch number 110773-200611) were purchased from the China National Institute for the Control of Pharmaceutical and Biological Products. Rhubarb anti-injury cataplasm was provided by Shanghai Traditional Chinese Medicine Pharmaceutical Technology Co. Ltd. Rhubarb, raw gardenia, ginseng, angelica, angelica, safflower, camellia, Wangbuliuxing, trichosanthes, red peony, turmeric, frankincense, myrrh 14 traditional Chinese medicines including camphor purchased from Shanghai Wanshicheng Pharmaceutical Co. Ltd.

Sample preparation

An aliquot of 0.5g of the rhubarb cataplasm was mixed with 25mL analytical reagent (AR) grade methanol, ultrasonicated three times (2 min each time), and incubated overnight at room temperature for maximum extraction. 1g of rhein and 0.5mg of ferulic acid were mixed with 1000 mL and 1mL of AR grade methanol

and followed to ultrasonication for 30 and 20 min, respectively. The rhein and ferulic acid extraction were dissolved by chloroform and methanol, after which the solutions were collected for the study.

Thin-layer chromatography (TLC)

TLC is a very delicate method for examining mixtures to separate the compounds. The silica gel G prefabricated plates were used to run TLC. An aliquot of 10 μ L of 100 mg/mL methanolic extracts were added to the plates by the Linomat 5 applicator (CAMAG, Muttenz, Switzerland). The developing agent is petroleum ether (30~60°C)-Ethyl formate-formic acid (15:5:1) upper layer solution, inspected under ultraviolet light (365nm).

TLC method was adopted for identification of *Rhei radix et Rhizoma*, *Swertia pseudochinensis* Hara in the prescription. The content of aloemodin, chrysophanol, and physcion in Dahuang Qushang Cataplasm formulation was determined by HPLC. The mobile phase consisted of methanol and 0.1% H₃PO₄ (70:30, V/V) with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min, and the detection wavelength was set at 254 nm.

Results

TLC identification of rhubarb

TLC is a very delicate method used for examining mixtures by separating the compounds in the mixture. This supportive technique is used to find the number of components in a given mixture, like the purity of a compound and the identity of compounds. The progress of a reaction can also be monitored through this technique by observing the disappearance of a reactant or the appearance of a product [Rchana A. Bele et al 2010](#); [Isabelle A. Kagan et al 2014](#).

Take 0.1g of rhubarb reference medicinal material, prepare the reference medicinal material solution; carry out the test according to the "Chinese Pharmacopoeia" [10] thin-layer chromatography. In the solution chromatogram of the test substance, fluorescent spots of the same colour appear, and the negative control substance has no interference. The chromatogram is shown in Figure 1A. After fumigation in ammonia gas, the spots are visible, and the negative control substance has no interference (Figure 1B). Next, we take 10 μ L of Angelica reference medicinal solutions and spot them on the silica gel G thin-layer plate. The developing solvent is cyclohexane-dichloromethane-ethyl acetate-formic acid (4:1:1:0.1) inspected under UV light (365nm). The same fluorescent spots are displayed in the test solution chromatogram, and the same colour fluorescent spots are displayed on the corresponding positions of the control medicinal material solution chromatogram and the reference substance solution chromatogram. The negative control has no interference. The chromatogram is shown in Figure 1C.

Figure 1. TLC chromatography of (A) *Rhei radix et Rhizoma*, (B) *Rhei radix et Rhizoma*, and (C) *Swertia*. Panel 1 represent; Reference solution, 2; Reference material solution, panel 3-5; Test solutions, and 6; Negative reference solution *pseudochinensis* Hara.

In the chromatogram of the test sample, there are five orange-yellow fluorescent main spots at the position corresponding to the chromatogram of the control solution; at the position corresponding to the chromatogram of the reference substance, there are the same orange fluorescent spots. After fumigation in ammonia vapor, the spots turn red (Figure 2). The negative blank has no interference.

Methodological investigation

Take the reference solution, the test solution, and the negative reference solution, inject 10 μ L of the sample according to the chromatographic conditions in 2.2.1, and record the chromatogram. The negative reference solution of this product did not interfere with the chromatographic peaks of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether, which proved that the method established in this paper was highly specific.

Figure 2. The chromatography assay panel 1 represent rhein reference material, 2; rhubarb reference material, 3-5; Test solution, and 6; negative control solution.

Linear relationship investigation: Take aloe-emodin (58.80 μ g/ml), chrysophanol (159.00 μ g/ml) emodin methyl ether (53.46 μ g/ml) mixed reference solution, and measure 2, 1.5, 1, 0.5, 0.25 respectively, 0.2, 0.1mL
 North American Academic Research, 5(1) | January 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7490275> | Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 19

to 2mL volumetric flask, dilute to the mark with methanol, respectively inject 10µl, and determine. Linear regression analysis with the concentration of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether as the abscissa and the peak area as the ordinate shows that the aloe-emodin is in the range of 2.94-58.80µg/ml and the chrysophanol is in the range of 7.95-159.00µg/ml. Within the range, emodin methyl ether is in the range of 2.67-53.46µg/ml, and the peak area has a good linear relationship (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Results of linear relationship investigation

Tested components	Regression equation	r value	Linear range (µg/ml)
Aloe-emodin	$y = 39.009x - 12.403$	0.9998	2.94-58.80
Chrysophanol	$y = 42.286x - 46.11$	0.9998	7.95-159.00
Emodin methyl ether	$y = 27.735x - 13.347$	0.9998	2.67-53.46

Precision test: Take aloe-emodin (7.35µg/ml), chrysophanol (19.88µg/ml), emodin methyl ether (6.68µg/ml) mixed reference solution, and inject 6 consecutive samples according to the planned chromatographic conditions. The average peak areas of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether were 282.5, 822.3, and 179.6. The RSD values were 0.14%, 0.07%, and 0.57%, respectively, indicating that the instrument's precision was good.

Repeatability test: We take one piece of Rhubarb Qushang Pabu (batch number 200806), prepare the test solution, and determine the content of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether according to the proposed chromatographic conditions. The average total content of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether was 1.06 mg/tablet, and the RSD was 2.42% (n=6), indicating that the method has good repeatability.

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) assay

We took three batches of samples, each with one sticker, prepared the test solution, injected the sample according to the chromatographic conditions, recorded the peak area, and calculated the sample content. The total contents of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether in the three batches of samples were 1.04, 1.04, and 1.07 mg, respectively, with an average value of 1.05 mg and an RSD of 1.65% (n=3). It is finally determined that the total content of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether in the finished product should not be less than 0.85mg per patch (Figure 3).

Figure 3. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) assay. In the assay (a) Mixed reference solution, (b) Test solution, and (c) Negative reference solutions were used. Peak 1 represent; Aloeemodin, 2; Chrysophanol, and 3; Physcion.

Discussion

The TLC spots were clear, and the blank test showed no interference. The average value of total content of aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and physcion was 1.05mg and RSD was 1.65% (n=3).

Rhubarb is the prince medicine in the prescription of rhubarb anti-injury patches. It has the effects of clearing heat and purging fire, cooling blood and detoxification, removing blood stasis, and clearing menstruation [Jin Lixia et al 2020](#). Studies have shown that its main components are aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether. Anthraquinone derivatives such as emodin and rhein, these components have diarrhea, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and other effects that can improve the inflammatory response caused by soft tissue injury [Zhang Xianghong et al 2009](#). In the early stage of this experiment, referring to the requirements for determining rhubarb content in the Pharmacopoeia of the People's Republic of China, aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, emodin methyl ether, emodin, and rhein were selected as the inspection indicators. The peak area is small, and the peak height is low. The effect of including the two into the quality control indicators is not satisfactory [Huang Juan et al 2014](#); [Cai Xinjie et al 2018](#). Finally, aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether are selected as the quality control indicators.

The mobile phase consists of the methanol-phosphoric acid system [Qiao Liye et al 2015](#); [Shi Wenbin et al 2016](#), [Li Ping et al 2013](#), an acetonitrile-phosphoric acid system [Liu Bingwang et al 2014](#); [Zhang Shibo et al 2018](#), methanol-acetic acid system. The preliminary experiment refers to the mobile phase conditions for determining rhubarb content in the Chinese Pharmacopoeia. The use of methanol-0.1% phosphoric acid solution (85:15) cannot separate aloe-emodin, chrysophanol, and emodin methyl ether well. Many differences are investigated [Xu Shouzhu et al 2010](#). After the proportion of methanol-0.1% phosphoric acid solution as the mobile phase, it was found that the peak shape and resolution of the chromatographic peaks in the spectrum obtained from methanol-0.1% phosphoric acid solution (70:30) were the best. Finally, the mobile phase was determined to be methanol-0.1% phosphoric acid solution. (70:30).

The TLC chromatograph, shown in Figure 1, is taken over the TLC plates where silica gel is the stationary phase while the solvent is the mobile phase. It has been shown that in Figure 1B, nothing is appeared, which means the compound has not been separated. However, Figure 1A with the reference solution shows the single bright spot, which means the compound is there without separation. In Figure 1 C, the separation of Swertia showed with large spot area. The consistent change has been shown in Figures 1A and 1C for the mobile phase numbers 2-6. Figure 2 shows the HPLC chromatograms of the mixed reference solution, test solution, and negative reference solution designated as a, b, and c. High-performance liquid chromatography explains about to separate, identify and quantify the amount of sample. The two major peaks observed in the plot represent hydrophilic (1) and hydrophobic (2). From Figure 2, it has been observed that the concentration absorption of a hydrophobic compound is more as compared to the hydrophobic compound. However, in the presence of test and negative reference solutions, the concentration absorption was also going to decrease.

Conclusion

Rhubarb is a family member of Polygonaceae, which is known for its flowering plants or informally as smartweed. The techniques of high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and thin-layer chromatography (TLC) used for the treatment are very reliable and accurate. The quality of Dahuang Qushang Cataplasm can be effectively controlled with these methods. The TLC result shows that a single bright spot was observed with the reference solution, which means the compound is not separated. The separation of Swertia was observed with a large spot area for Figure 1C. The more precise separation, purification, and quantification of the sample done with HPLC show the separation of hydrophilic and hydrophobic organic molecules. The intensity of these hydrophilic molecules in mobile phase mixed reference solution, test solution, and negative reference solution found to be decline consistently for aloe-emodin (a), chrysophanol (b), and physcion (c). However, the intensity of hydrophobic molecules was found to be less compared to hydrophilic.

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